

COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGY OF THE PLURAL FORM OF NOUNS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotation: The objective of the article is to provide the analysis of plurality of noun and the difference in the use of Uzbek and English nouns explains their place in the sentence as well as their structure. The similarity of the names in Uzbek and English reveals different aspects.

In this article the forming plurality of nouns in the Uzbek and English languages is analyzed, disparities in the use of Uzbek and English nouns in sentences and contexts are explained and aspects of similarities of some names in both languages are revealed.

Аннотация: Цель статьи является провести анализ множественности существительных, а разница в употреблении узбекских и английских существительных объясняет их место в предложении, а также их структуру. Сходство названий на узбекском и английском языках раскрывает разные аспекты.

Key words: noun, plurality, comparison, similarity, category.

Introduction A noun is a word that names something, such as a person, place, thing, or idea. In a sentence, nouns can play the role of subject, direct object, indirect object, subject complement, object complement, appositive, or adjective.

Comparative typology learns similarities and differences among two or more languages grammar, phonetics, stylistics etc.

Uzbek nouns and pronouns usually use the suffix *-lar* (e.g. *odam-lar*, *muttaham-lar*) to indicate this number, which is sometimes used to show respect for the person mentioned. Example: people died.

This category can be expressed in two languages through individual personal information. EX. : I-WE; Me; It is the same. In the middle: your own employment; *Yoshlar*. From a lexical point of view, this category can be numerically represented in both languages.

Examples: *dual-ikkilik*, *major-ko'pchilik*, *family-oila*, *pair-juft*, *double-ikki* etc. Plurals can sometimes be expressed in the form of prepositions (middle), indefinite pronouns (some, several), verbs (one, gather –*to'plamaq*), number signs (two-place, multi-level, two-story): and Uzbek languages *qo'sharik*, *uchko'prik*).

Typological categories of personality

The category of people should be considered in close connection with the category (plural) of numbers. In the languages of the Indo-European family, these categories are simultaneously represented by the same morphemes. In other words, morphemes that represent numbers also represent people. For example, the n+ morpheme in Latin is amant, habent, Legunt, amabant, habebunt, etc. Represents third person and plural at the same time.

In comparative languages, categories of people are characteristic of nouns and verbs. They (languages) distinguish two classes of personal pronouns, each representing a person (person) (second person) and the person(s) (or things) referred to (third person).

Singular plural

Person 1 is the speaker and the others are

Person 2 is a person talking to several people.

Person 3 is the person talking about a person or thing.

There is no notion that countable and uncountable nouns in Uzbek instead of this they can use measurements of uncountable nouns such as: bir qoshiq choy- a spoon of tea, bir kosa sho'rva- a bowl of soup.

A system of grammatical forms indicating a grammatical grade (a number) is called a plural (named) category. this category. When comparing languages, formants representing this category are usually added to the noun (or pronoun) root. We must distinguish between logical numbers (degrees) and grammatical numbers. Logically, proper nouns usually refer to the same thing or person. For example: John, Sobir, London, To'ytepa, etc. Common nouns are, of course, logically used to refer to two or more common things.

As is well known, plural categories refer only to a single entity, person or phenomenon. Grammatically, in English the zero morpheme and the suffixes -s, -en can be collated and are based on the ability to shift the stem of some nouns: i.e. -s, -en, in Uzbek based on collation. Morphemes and suffixes - lar, ie - ar. Among the parts of the sentence, this category is grammatically distinguished as nouns, pronouns and verbs.

In English, the plural form of some nouns is made through a change in the stem while in uzbek the plural form of nouns is made only through the suffix - lar. For instance :ox-oxen, child-children, woman-women, buqa-buqalar, bola-bolalar, ayol-ayollar.

The usage of plural nouns from a syntactic point of view both languages.

In Uzbek, plural nouns are used usually after subject of sentence and acted as a indirect object.

Men bolalarni yaxshi ko'raman.

In English, plural nouns utilize after predicative of sentence and acted as a indirect object. This is also similarity of syntax in both languages.

Sarah is watching films.

In verbs, the category of person is expressed in the first, second and third person and refers to the relationship between the speaker, speaker or people and another person or people. However, this system does not apply to modern English verbs, for two reasons:

1) There is no difference between plurals. Therefore, this form can be connected with the subject of a plural person.

Live we he

2) There is no difference between 1st and 2nd person numbers. Thus, a "living" object of this person can represent more than one subject. So the contradiction means that any other person 3 belongs to two numbers of people, i.e. stem-\stem-i. The marked location part differs significantly in form and meaning from the printed part. In the subjunctive forming the form "life", both numbers refer to a person.

The "end" with four simultaneous meanings is certainly a singular synthetic feature in the general structure of modern English. In English, there are special verb families that do not fit into the person and number systems described above, which must be considered separately in both practical and theoretical analysis of the language. "can, maybe, must", etc. becomes an assistant. Because it is an optional verb, it does not attach a suffix to the root, does not denote a person or a number, and usually accompanies a pseudo-verb in speech to give additional meaning to a concept such as ability, permission, necessity, or duty.

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